

THE MINIMUM CELL

Family and households in new housing proposals

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Abstract

This study tries to reflect upon dwellers that will take part in recent and future housing proposals through new experiments under spatial and formal offers.

It is supported upon a reflection based in the so-called social housing that have been proposed mainly since the beginning of the 20th century, without ignoring the philanthropic experiments that were tried since the beginning of the industrial revolution.

From them aroused the questions of idealization or observation of the dwellers: in the first case through a conception of an idealistic family or household who would lead to a better society; in the second case, the attempt to respond to the existing dweller creating a proposal to better respond immediate needs for shelter and to identify himself with his own house.

Throughout past and present experiments, it will be offered the opportunity to prepare, rather than predict, our responses to future challenges in housing.

Keywords: Housing; Function; Family; Household

1. Concept: Minimum as Family

The idealization of minimum criteria in architecture has always been based in practical needs. The urgent response to a chronic shortage of housing for the poorest pressured the philanthropic and architectural community to devise ways of solving the lack of physical and psychological dignity in worker's houses. Therefore, it will be made an investigation about the way houses have been designed according to their intended dwellers. The concept of 'family' has been proven to be a fragile definition of the house's users, since there are other possibilities of residence other than those defined by blood-

ties. It will be sought in this chapter the identification of the domestic space with its dwellers, where several architectural theories try to formalize its models as a response to the household, rather than providing a mere practical shelter.

2. Inhabiting a Home: Uses and Symbols

As an evolutionary process, the architectural house was once the social manifestation of those with the possibilities to do so, before the adoption of some of its symbols by vernacular and popular architecture that tried to transform a house into something more than a physical protection.

2.1. Erudite Domestic Architecture

2.1.1. The 'Enfilade'

Figure 1: spatial sequence according to Alberti

Alberti (1404-1472) in his treatise 'De re Aedificatoria' describe the ideal house within the visitor's point of view: a course initiated in a square space, followed by circular one, a new polygon, ending at the heart of the house, a space defined by straight lines and curves. Although very generic, it's an example how the erudite house was define according to its symbolism.

Figure 2: spatial sequence according to D. Duarte

This sequenced spatial solution (the enfilade) was also referred later by D. Duarte in the aristocratic house from the XV century, where the successive spaces evolved from public to private: first, a welcoming area, then a space accessible to only some noble gentleman, a sleeping room, a dressing room and finally an oratory, the last resort of intimacy.

2.1.2. The Corridor

Figure 3: first apartments in previous multi-storey family town house

The first urban apartments were born from a single multi-storey family house, where several rooms formed an apartment that had to share a common staircase with all its neighbors. When the apartment started to be defined in one single floor, the 'enfilade' became a useful feature in the design of a scheme that started in a reception room, then the sleeping room, a 'cabinet', and finally the dressing room (always using the public/private sequence, where all the utilitarian rooms were excluded¹).

The 1755 earthquake in Lisbon, through the necessary reconstruction of the downtown city ('Baixa Pombalina'), gave the possibility to experiment some new spatial features in city planning, but also in

¹ Barreiros, Maria Helena, 2004, 'Casas em cima de casas: apontamentos sobre o espaço doméstico da baixa pombalina', in Revista Monumentos n.º 21, September 2004, Direcção Geral dos Edifícios e Monumentos Nacionais, Lisbon

new dwellings that offered a 'new' room, a hall-type space that consisted in a limit between the public staircase and the house². More important was the corridor, introduced sideways to the 'enfilade', allowing the access to each room without disturbing the previous one. This meant that now each space could be given a specific use independently from its position in a sequence.

Figure 4: 'Baixa Pombalina' building: ground-floor, entresol, first floor, second floor and above

Although distant from social housing, this example tries to make us understand the transformations among the house's character that would perspire to more modest dwells, but also that the criteria applied in the organization of the dwelling did not always considered the dwellers as an unique entity, like a family. Another point of view can be taken into consideration, this time trying to see the (master's) house as a physical manifestation of the family's DNA: being the layout of the house defined by the 'intensity' of privacy, it would be normal to join their activities according to their need for seclusion, as a group: the room where the parents slept, ate, rested and played with their children was the same, preceded by an 'apparatus room' for the visitors, but followed by a dressing room and an 'oratory/boudoir' where women started to write their diaries once they had access to literacy.

The distinction between public and private is still common in our houses but in the above examples the hierarchy is defined according to the paternal/maternal figures and not the family as a whole. Along in this hierarchy children did not have a specific space or a role, understood as single entity, making possible to declare that the entity that gave structure to the house was not the family but the couple.

3. Space and Hierarchy: Domestic Procedures

This brief itinerary trough erudite architecture seems taken out of context, but it precedes the first popular housing models. For instance, it is important to explain the meaning of 'Popular' in our present discussion.

² Loyer, François, 1987, *Paris XIXe siècle, l'immeuble et la rue*, Paris : Fernand Hazan [ISBN 2 85025 121 6]

In the present context we will use ‘Popular’ but something that is ‘made for the people’, contrary to the definition used in studies about Vernacular, Popular and Erudite architecture³ where it’s discussed unequivocally something that comes ‘from the people’.

3.1. Prelude 1

The Vernacular and Popular house always had some spontaneity, since there was no theoretical debate over them. In this particular context we are still away from nowadays, searching for the moment where the dweller became the basis of the architectural debate. But even in the more remote examples the vernacular house was more than a shelter, like in Skara Brae, a Neolithic village located in Scotland. The houses were circular structures with a central fireplace where a series of elements and furniture defined a precise circular path which culminated in a ‘stone cabinet’, a utilitarian space destined to the matriarch (the patriarch sat at the fireplace, in front of the entrance). So, just like in an erudite Model we can identify a Patriarchal organization defining space even without walls or doors.

Figure 5: typical house in Skara Brae

3.2. Prelude 2

The first philanthropic movements in England comprised mainly the rural house, since it occurred before the first migrations to the cities caused by the industrial revolution. There were created models of housing for rural workers, supposedly adapted to the needs of its idealized dwellers. John Plaw (1745-1820), for instance, is one of the few that manages to offer models with a real practical sense (rather than making a mere aesthetically romantic investigation), in its dimensions and materials.

³ **Jorge, Pedro Fonseca, 2006, ‘Tipos de Arquitectura’,** in ‘*A casa rural no Concelho de Alcobaça em 1961: da teorização Erudita à prática Popular*’, Thesis for the Master Degree in ‘Methods of Intervention in Architectural Heritage’, FAUP 2006, pages. 16 to 49.

Figure 6: proposed rural housing models, by John Plaw

Like in the previous examples we can still find a patriarchal/matriarchal solution where the parents' privacy is an emphasized feature: there is only one room, for them, while children still use the utilitarian spaces to sleep. The models also presented a series of annexes, like a pantry or a space for firewood that leads us to think that the main effort was applied in satisfying practical needs.

4. The First Popular Models: countryside/urban solutions

4.1. Being Popular in the Countryside

The beginning of the Industrial Revolution didn't occur in the cities, but in less centralized areas, where space and resources were available. But even in the countryside migration occurred and houses were needed for the once rural, now factory workers. One solution was the conversion of ancient farms, whose longitudinal buildings allowed the use of the row house typology. The models created from scratch had the same inconvenient, where houses were overlapped without any breathing areas or sunshine. So, like Schoenauer said⁴, there was a regression in one's life quality, since the rural model was a more spacious, isolated building, with extra room that prevented the use of the 'box-beds' offered by these models. This was the only resort of privacy in the entire house, where the same patriarchal family structure was applied.

4.1.1. Weaving against Horticulture

⁴ Schoenauer, Norbert, 2000, '6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition', New York: W. W. Norton & Company, [ISBN 0-393-73052-2]

Figure 7: Weaver's Tenements (1780) and Laborer's Cottage (1796)

Figure 8: Weaver's Tenements (1780) and Laborer's Cottage (1796); (Distribution schemes)

In the 1780 model destined to weaving factory workers we can recognize a building scheme with a central staircase that gives access to two apartments per floor. The inner spatial solution is the one mentioned above, where only 19 to 21m² serve the entire family with the referred 'box-bed' enclosed by a curtain. It doesn't sustain the comparison with the same period row houses for rural workers, who had 54m² distributed in three floors, but still one bedroom.

4.2. Being Popular in the City

4.2.1. Proposed Type

Among the studied models we must refer those proposed for a housing competition promoted by an American magazine by the end of the XVIII century. The briefing asked for Types of houses that could solve the lack of salubrity of the common New York apartment, born trough the internal division of town houses, with rooms without lighting or ventilation. The alternatives should consider very narrow and profound plots where light shafts would try to offer the necessary light and fresh air. In the selected proposals it's common the scheme were different rooms succeed, starting in the kitchen/dining room and ending in a more noble space, with windows facing the street. In some models there is another room between those two, sized to fit two beds. We can assume the biggest room as the resort of privacy for the parents, with the siblings staying in the small bedroom or even the kitchen.

Cell

Association of the Cell

Figure 9: Design Competition 2 (1879)

Being the more important space the bedroom (the only space facing the street), the above example sustains the existence of a 'linear family', that, as seen in erudite examples, it's not a question of area.

4.2.2. Existing Type

Although the inner 'course' of the house ends in the parents' room, it is still the masculine figure that dominates the family. The social distinction between man and woman was not obvious in the physical shape of the house, since the kitchen was attached to the 'dining room' without any kind of spatial hierarchy (although cooking and serving were tasks only a woman could perform).

In the late years of the XVIII century England was proposing small and simple housing models for factory workers, but in Holland there was a very common city apartment⁵ where the kitchen was an

⁵ French, Hilary, 2008, 'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century', London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, [ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0]

independent space next to the façade with more than 20% of the apartment's total area (37m²), even if bedrooms were still 'box beds'. Was this a first step in women's emancipation (through a more qualified workspace)? Or was it another way of segregation by enclosing her and her functions in a closed space?

Floor plans

View

Figure 10: XIX Century Dutch Apartment

5. The Mirror of the Family: Father, Mother, Sons and Daughters

5.1 Two Bedrooms

Until now there was little thought about children and their accommodations, as they made use of other areas. Therefore, when a properly lightened and ventilated second bedroom is added to the structure of the house, it demonstrated the children's different status within the family.

5.1.1. Streatham

This might be considered the first (1848-1849) of 'social housing' buildings for many reasons. Its author, Henry Roberts (1803-1876) intended to provide a whole solution to the social problems of the poorer beyond a mere shelter. Therefore he proposed a second bedroom with practically the same qualities as the main bedroom, and that in a city building, usually more pressured by speculation and profitability.

Figure 11: Streatham Building (1848), Henry Roberts (1803-1876)

This is a very meaningful change, since other contemporary proposals, like the ‘bylaw houses’, designed to comply to new health regulation, who were double storey row houses, still didn’t have any evolutions according to this criteria. Like the Dutch model, Streatham has the same 37m², so area was not a motive for the inner cell differences. There is a different ideology that considered promiscuity a question of mental health, as important as physical. This lead to the transformation of the domestic space in a more profound way than an independent kitchen would do (Streatham proposes only a pantry that complements the living/dining/kitchen).

Floor Plans

View and association of the cells

Figure 12: ‘Bylaw Houses’ (1853)

5.1.2: Van Beuningstraat

In 1909 Van der Pek (1865-1919) proposed a Type with two rooms, lounge and kitchen, all of them correctly lightened through windows facing the street (there is variation of this Type in the first floor that still has box beds - requested by tenants – but they don't replace any bedroom). We must mention van der Pek's social activism in the achievement of this solution, since he thought that housing was one of the most important ways to obtain changes to the society. He considered the English models as mere reduced bourgeois houses, arguing that new housing proposals must correspond to worker's expectations and needs.

Figure 13: Van Beuningenstraat (1909), Jans Ernst van der Pek (1865 – 1919)

5.2. Three Rooms

The need of the tenants of Van Beuningenstraat for the additional box beds in their flats was not only dictated by ancient ways of living, at least not entirely: at first, in these models they seem dispensable, since there were already two bedrooms. However, a truly absence of promiscuity, has the philanthropists intended, would only be achieved if it could be a separation according to the siblings genre. A three-bedroom apartment wouldn't be a luxury but the necessary evolution in order to provide true privacy.

5.2.1 Spangen

Ten years after Van Beuningenstraat, Michiel Brinkman designs the Spangen Quarter in Rotterdam, where he tries to strengthen society through the individual. The three-bedroom flat is therefore a conscientious choice, like a foundation for the development of the person. Brinkman only has 3 to 4m² more than van der Pek's apartments to design his three bedroom house, but still he manages to offer the additional room by diminishing the other rooms' areas, proving that for him even a 5,5m² bedroom was better than no bedroom at all. Also corridors and an entrance hall were provided in an attempt to promote privacy not only within the apartment but also for outside's prying eyes.

Floor plan (ground floor)

View from the pateo

Figure 14: Spangen (1919), Michiel Brinkman (1873 – 1925)

Trough the floor plan we can identify a Modern solution: a private or nighttime area, a dwellers' public or daytime area, and a service area (kitchen and bathroom, around the entrance hall). Because his architectural language had little to do with the Modern Movement, Brinkman is for some an 'empirical classicist'⁶, which already means some recognition of his effort in the conception of the inner spaces of the housing cell. But according to his premises of observing people's lives as a basis of his architecture, it would be more accurate to define him as a 'classical functionalist'.

5.2.2 Bad Dürrenberg

The period between the two World Wars was fertile in experiments in the field of social or subsidized housing. In three years four exemplar projects are concluded exhibiting four different approaches to domestic life, proving that was impossible to unit all architectural practice under the aegis of terminologies like Modernism, Functionalism or International Style.

Figure 15: Praunheim (1926); Karl Marx Hof (1926); Weissenhof (1927); Bad Dürrenberg (1928)

⁶ **Lambla, Ken**, 2009, – *Abstraction and theosophy: social housing in Rotterdam, The Netherlands*, <<http://corbu2.caed.kent.edu/architronic/v8n1/v8n104.pdf>> [01.2009]

Ernst May (Praunheim, 1926); Karl Ehn (Karl Marx Hof, 1926), Mies van der Rohe (Weissenhof Apartments, 1927) and Alexander Klein (Bad Dürrenberg, 1928) testify that diversity. Among them, Klein tries to mirror the existing family type in its proposal in a rather rigid manner with a severely functionalist solution, a result that would affiliate him in the European contemporary avant-garde movements, if only his language would be more 'Modern'. An entrance hall, a laboratory kitchen (strictly for cooking), a lounge with a dining area close to the kitchen, a corridor for the private spaces like bathroom and the 'children's' bedrooms' (in his own words). The master bedroom, according to the apartment modular solution was accessed through the lounge or even by one of the previous bedrooms.

His exaggerated functionalism makes him observe all the family types that were common in the period so he could create a unique and exclusive solution for each of them. His cells were 'static' in the sense that they would only fully adapt to its tenants at the moment of the 'observation', not being capable sustain future evolution (like the addition of one or more family members).

The C2 cell it's strictly conceived for only three occupants: father/mother and one child. The measurements of the children's bedroom were scientifically determined (with a method created by him) to accommodate one bed, one desk and one chair. If the couple had one more same-sex children, then they had to choose (or move to) the C9 cell, who had more 5m² in the bedroom for another bed, another desk and another chair. But if their children had different genres, then the solution would be the C7 cell with two of the C2 single bedroom. Finally, if the children were more than two, there was the C17 cell with two of the C9 double rooms... The lounge would evolve in each of these solutions but the laboratory-like kitchen would maintain its area.

Cell 'C2'

Cell 'C9'

Cell 'C7'

Cell 'C17'

Figure 16: Bad Dürrenberg (1928), Alexander Klein (1879 – 1961)

Nevertheless the addition of a third bedroom was a huge change, since the Karl Marx Hof, two years earlier, offered mainly one bedroom flats with the same floor area as the two bedroom C2 cell (53m²). Karl Ehn's solution was based in a more ancient conception of the house that still polarized the family structure in the parents (ignoring the children as individuals)

One bedroom apartment

Outside view

Figure 17: Karl Marx Hof (1926), Karl Ehn (1884 – 1957 or 1959)

Nevertheless, Klein's surgical proposals created typologies that are still common nowadays, like the functional separation that would be current for decades. However, the third room was already a big achievement: the single room for each son would have to wait some more years.

5.3. More Rooms

In the next examples we can find some models that offer supplemental spaces to the original structure of a two or three-bedroom apartment. This was not yet associated to the desire to offer each son a room, but it was born under the analysis of family structures that added more elements to the basic nuclear family (parents/sons).

5.3.1. Praunheim

Ernst May's 'New Frankfurt' is well known for many reasons, mainly for being a well executed series of small garden cities around Frankfurt. Unlike the original English garden-city, May conceives them closer to the city core, making it more plausible. As a functionalist, he works with Grete Schütte-Lihotsky (1897-2000) in order to conceive the 'Frankfurt Kitchen', a prefabricated structure based on a thorough analysis of the housewife's activities while cooking. This 'laboratory' would be included in all of the 'New Frankfurt' housing typologies, Praunheim included.

Figure 18: Praunheim (1926), Ernst May (1886 – 1970)

Intended to be one step forward in women's emancipation (since it would simplify their tasks, now that they were part of the family's working members), the 'Frankfurt Kitchen' was actually another way to segregate them. Cooking is still their exclusive task, an additional labor to the factory work already done during the day. And now, instead of cooking in a 'traditional' kitchen were all the family got together, they are now kept apart in a tiny cubicle with a small opening where dishes are passed trough. Intended as a step forward, this was a regression where even the part of the woman as a designer is called in to question: she was still an accessory to the main architect's work, also like Charlotte Perriand, Corbusier's partner in furniture design and... the 'Unité d'Habitation' kitchens.

Nowadays' replica

Grete Schütte-Lihotsky

Figure 19: 'Frankfurt Kitchen'

The internal layout of the Praunheim cells was not something very innovative, somehow common in other functionalist proposals: parent's bedroom, children's bedroom (in his own words), without gender distinction. The master bedroom is always bigger than the children's (16m² for 8m² in the Type IIA), which remembers the above mentioned family structure defined by a couple and an amalgam of children. The master bedroom's additional area does not only define hierarchy but it allows the couple's private development as an entity by giving them additional private space for other activities in the bedroom (a need that is not acknowledged for the children or adolescents). In the above mentioned Type IIA there is a room defined as 'loft' in the upper floor of the house, with a huge balcony that actually is an extension of the master bedroom.

Figure 20: Type IIA cell, Praunheim

At a glance the Type VII looks similar to the previous one, but in fact its loft corresponds to a nuclear family that has been expanded: the loft is no longer an extension of a room, but a separate entity altogether, since it has an independent entrance, becoming a flat within the house. It has kitchen, bathroom and an open space for lounging and sleeping. Usually the floor plans have captions that identify the bedrooms as parent's and children's, but this loft has no precise user attached. So it is a space for multiple purposes than can accommodate grandparents, uncles or even a recently married son or daughter.

Figure 21: Type VII cell, Praunheim

This would be a breakthrough since usually the family was idealized as a static entity where the characters 'maintain the same age forever', forgetting those periods where the family's boundaries are toned down (and where the entity of a 'household' would be more pertinent than the conception of a 'family'). However this is an example of a very rigid initial module that has to repeat utilitarian spaces (like kitchen and bathroom) to become versatile, instead of promoting flexibility from the start.

5.4. Several Rooms

Mies proposals contemplate rigid layouts and open spaces, tiny kitchens (3m²) and livable ones (13m²); well defined nocturnal areas or bedrooms with sliding doors opened to the lounge. And finally, very common layouts and others more difficult to digest.

Figure 23: Weissenhof (1927), Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969), Second Floor (above), Ground and First Floors (below)

Mies probably didn't conceive this proposals as unalterable, like a catalogue in which the client would chose their preferred flat. As a display of possibilities, it would be also a demonstration of how the dweller could intervene in its own space, adapting it to changing circumstances as time went by.

Figure 24: Weissenhof (1927), Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969)

6. The Family Dismemberment

Functionalism believed in the development of the family structure according to a mechanical idea, where people would function within their homes with the same efficiency as in a factory. Nevertheless

they still believed that the basis of the society was the family, even if an idealized one. The Socialist revolution that occurred in the Soviet Union led to a new conception of society: all notions of classes would be eliminated, including the main expression of the bourgeoisie, the Family. Blood ties were considered inappropriate for the development of an egalitarian society where the only collective element would be a community made only by individuals. The couple was accounted as two independent elements, and their main function was to evolve physically and mentally, in which the family and its duties were an obstacle. From now on raising and educating children would be a social duty performed by trained educators and not the parents.

This inhumane proposal of social organization would reveal inadequate and far from the aspirations of the future dwellers who would live in future housing proposals conceived under these theories. In an inquiry made to the Russian population promoted by OSA (Contemporary Architects Association), which defended a less pragmatic posture than ASNOVA (New Architects Association), people said that they didn't want English 'cottages' to live, but even less 'apartment cages'. They still defended the family as the society and house basic element⁸.

6.1. The Social Condenser

Despite this enquiry, some models were designed according to this 'new' society. The model building would be made out of units composed by a lounge and a room for one person, where he could have his personal space. All the interaction with his colleagues, friends and family would be made in the canteen or the Worker's Club. Karel Teige defined the housing block as a sum of these cells, with a total occupation of 400 to 800 dwellers (100 to 125 traditional families) distributed through only five stories so they wouldn't have a lift and could be built traditionally.

6.1.1. The 'Dom-Kommuna' Narkomfin

This building is the best known expression of the new social order, destined to house the employees of the Ministry of Finance (Narkomfin). Its author, Moisei Ginzburg (1892-1946), conceived it as a transition for the new society, since the intended changes in people's habits would be too dramatic. There's still a canteen and a Worker's Club, but the base-unit of the cells would be the couple (with or without children) and not the individual. It had a little bathroom, a small kitchen counter (that would be removed once society had evolved to use only collective services) and it was it. As Teige, he also agreed that the 'Frankfurt Kitchen' was useless and degrading for women. We are still far from the beehive intended by Teige, but close to his idealized cell: a comfortably sized private space (bedroom: 21m²;

⁸ **Aymonino, Carlo**, 1973, "*La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930*", Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029, 1973, [ISBN 84-252-0755-X]

lounge: 24m²) so there could be a personal area away from children. Its galleries and double height ceilings would inspire Corbusier (1887-1965), which according to him ‘respired Modernity’.

Figure 25: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin (1927), Moisei Ginzburg (1892 - 1946)

Even if Teige’s extremist ideas were not put into practice, the toned-down ‘Social Condenser’ wouldn’t be accepted. It consisted in the ‘cages’ dreaded by people, and it promoted an urban solution without a core or references. The Communist Regime would eventually prefer a classical image for its buildings in order to soothe the Russians in the post-revolutionary period⁹.

Figure 26: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin (1927), Moisei Ginzburg (1892 - 1946)

Although the ‘Dom-kommunas’ were a failure according to their main objective, its typology nowadays deserves a second outlook, since its studio-like apartments seem to fit the needs of new types of

⁹ **Teige, Karel** – “*The Minimum Dwelling*”, 2002, The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts [ISBN 0-262-20136-4]

households, like friends, bachelors or couples without children. These new characters would create the new 'household' figure, in which the family is just one of its components.

Figure 27: The 'Dom-kommuna' Narkomfin today

7. The Perseverance of the Family: shape and image

The post-II World War years were beneficial to the idea of the Family as the basis of the living cell. After the previous failed radical experiences, the minimum house investigation recovers some of the previous spatial solutions, even some brought by Modernism proved to be effective. But the hegemony that was intended by its authors was far from being attained and each country starts to search for new housing solutions within their frontiers. Instead of trying to do radical changes in the way of life, architects started to observe how people lived according to their own traditions, and trying to conceive the 'new house' starting from there. That would be one of the causes that would call Modernism into question.

7.1 Public over private

So, the liberty (from dogmas) allowed by the Modern revisionist movements permitted a greater attention to the surrounding reality. As a more visible consequence the International Style dilutes and the architecture general image becomes more humane. The internal space of the cell now makes references to local ways of life, which are still based on the Family, but impose different limits for their member's privacy according to the country they stand. Northern European countries reveal to be less complicated in the family's inner relationship, proposing bigger daytime areas, not as welcome areas, but in a way that considers intimate only the more personal activities (therefore with smaller bedrooms).

7.2 Private over Public

Southern Europe as a different understanding of privacy in which each member has the opportunity to get more in touch with their intimacy. The rooms are bigger, but also the family's activities are

maintained private from outside guests. A big kitchen with a dining table keeps more secluded meals and other activities performed within the family. So, the internal separation between daytime and nighttime areas proposed by Functionalism suited the Italian Neo-realism who esteemed their privacy.

7.3 Rethinking Modernism

Although some Modernist values were still valid, in the 60s some voices started to be heard defending the revision of its principles towards new ideas, shapes and image in architecture. However the themes that urgently needed debate were other than the Dweller, even if he still was indirectly affected by questions as urban planning or architectural heritage.

7.3.1 Urban Humanization

An anonymous urban image composed by isolated and identical housing blocks demanded new proposals that could once again transmit a sense of belonging. The relationship between shape and psychological needs becomes the theme of the last CIAM (Congrès Internationaux d'Architecture Moderne) in which the TEAM X intended to rethink some of the more simplistic Modern ideas. Allison and Peter Smithson were two of its members and their proposal took shape in the Robin Hood Gardens housing blocks, a three dimension critique to Corbusier's Ville Radieuse: the functional division among work/house/leisure was intended to be substituted by a sequence of house-street-district and city (the house being the primary unit of the process). The open galleries would represent those streets but they would reveal themselves inappropriate for communal living and a very weak alternative for courtyards, for instance.

Figure 28: Robin Hood Gardens (1966 - 1972), Allison e Peter Smithson (1928 - 1993; 1923 - 2003)

7.3.2 Aesthetical Humanization

From the 50s it became obvious that modernism had been an experience with little influence outside the architectural context, without making the changes it proposed. It remained as a style that managed to make everyplace look like anyplace¹⁰. The effort made over functionality and rationality forgot beauty, therefore Post-Modernism gives focus on the subject in order to hand back to architecture its symbols and context. The absence of new housing theories lead to the permanence of some Modernist types, even if revised. The more radical experiences were abandoned but a more softened Functionalism still remained.

Despite all its excesses Modernism accomplished a lot, by giving dignity to social housing, which became healthy, mentally and physically, not only through correct lighting and ventilation, but also throughout new spatial solutions, mainly spaces that promoted privacy. Although each culture started to recover some of its housing traditions, the bedroom was kept as an enclosed space.

8. New Characters in the Domestic Scene: the household

The modern nuclear family was the western idealization that determined the functional aspects of the house. It was linked to the family's means of subsistence and had evolved since the three generation family that took care of the crops before the industrial revolution. Such categorization was a simplistic one, since it excluded other agents that were not covered by the pre-establish model¹¹. The consequences were housing models that didn't fit the purposes of many households, like composed ones.

8.1 Identifying the Household

The 'household' appeared as a new categorization in which families, simple, composed or extended, are only part of the whole types of dwellers. In the United Kingdom in the 1971's Census there were already references to a Household, in which dwellers, family or not, should have some activities in common to be considered¹². Only in 1991 those activities were specified, like sharing a meal or the

¹⁰ **Frampton, Keneth**, (1996), *'Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna'*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, S.A. [ISBN 84-252-1628-1]

¹¹ *'Family in Anthropology since (1980) - New Directions For Family Studies'*, <<http://science.jrank.org/pages/9308/Family-in-Anthropology-since-1980-New-Directions-Family-Studies.html>>, [11.2008]

¹² *'Household definition on the census form'*, <<http://www.celsius.lshtm.ac.uk/modules/hhfam/hf020100.html>>, [11.2008]

lounge. Sylvia Yanagisako in a 1979¹³ article says that the Household is connected to residence, and not blood ties, in which the dweller's culture is reflected. Therefore a society's main domestic activities must be identified in order to define the criteria that will define the members of a household within that society. So, having meals together only is a criterion if in the corresponding society that is a habit.

8.1.1 Physical Preceding

Although recent, the household notion has always been present, even if it was an unintended and unwanted situation (like in the Industrial Revolution ages, where families had to share the same room with others).

8.1.2. Ideological Preceding

But even in the Modern Movement where the typical occupants of a house were the nuclear family, some architects seem to have based their proposals by observing real existing households, rather than creating an all-purpose type. Ernst May, being a functionalist, designs in Praunheim very 'restrict' cells, but also some that stand out for their spatial and functional features. The Type VII cell, already referred, has a loft in the upper floor that consists in an additional flat inside the house. Therefore a three generation enlarged household would find their place with additional privacy for an older or younger couple.

Figure 29: Type VII cell, **Praunheim** (1926), **Ernst May** (1886 – 1970)

8.2 Household's Evolution Elements

¹³ **Yanagisako, Sylvia**, 1979, "Family and Household: The Analysis of Domestic Groups", Annual Review of Anthropology, October 1979, Vol. 8, pages 161-205

We can admit that the alternative households would only account for a number of cases smaller than nowadays. The reasons that took to the creation of new households have to do with the evolving society in cultural terms (new kinds of relationship and privacy among dwellers) but also financially (for better or for worse). Therefore, the 'traditional' Modernist models start to show its frailty.

8.2.1 Economics as a Factor

After the II World War there was a huge reconstruction effort that made use of the Modernist spatial and constructive features. In countries where destruction was less acute, urgency was not an issue and there was the opportunity to experiment new housing solutions (like in the Nordic New Empiricism¹⁴). But the nuclear family stood as the used type, sometimes forgetting how difficult economics prevent one's independency, therefore creating additional household types trough enlarged families grown vertically (grandparents, parents, sons) or horizontally (parents, uncles, sons, nephews). If the house turns to be incapable of supporting a kind of use other than the one it was conceived to, the inter-relations among dwellers become fragile and less private. On the other hand, those who chose independency in the early years of their life can share the same house, therefore creating a household unrelated to blood-ties. Emigration is another factor that leads to coexistence among families in the same house, with the aggravating circumstance that the housing model, if strict in its physical use, is also culturally castrating.

8.2.2 Culture as a Factor

A swaying financial situation also leads to cultural changes within the household, as we seen above, and a beneficial economy has parallel consequences in the way we live. When college became more common, one of its consequences was to postpone young adults' independency. House sharing is a solution for displaced students, but for those close to home it means sharing a house with their parents. We must see beyond the family ties to understand that we are talking about adults from different age groups with a different cultural background, which makes coexistence more difficult. The functionalist model, severely divided in public, private and service, becomes obsolete since some 'services' become public (the kitchen), for example. In the composed households, with members in different group ages, it's created a gap, where we can identify visitors from each group that don't necessarily socialize among them.

¹⁴ **Fonseca Jorge, Pedro**, 2010, *'The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum'*, International Journal of Arts and Sciences (as presented in the International Conference for Academic Disciplines, Orlando 1-4 March 2010)

9. Redefining Parts: fatherhood, motherhood and brotherhood

Another cultural factor that would influence the development of the house since the late 1970's would be the (real) women's emancipation from its traditional part. It was attempted previously in Modernism, but as a paternalistic attitude that would keep women subdued: the simplification of the domestic tasks still implied that those tasks were exclusively hers. There are two aspects to take into account: first, the kitchen becomes more humane, losing its laboratorial look and isolation, and second it becomes an extension of the lounge.

9.1. Up North

This phenomenon was more visible in Central and Northern Europe, since its cultural history had always defined a less rigid separation between public and private: down south the kitchen kept its very private character, as a space for the family's inter-relationship. It is no longer a cubicle, but a spacious room, even if properly enclosed.

9.1.1: Kitchen with a space for meals

The second generation Modernism had already proposed a small dining area located after a corridor-kitchen, like in Alvar Aalto's Hansaviertel Apartments in 1955. But gradually this solution progressed to less liberal countries, like France, where the Emile Aillaude's (1902-1988) 'Tour Nuage' (1975) offers the same kitchen type. The 'corridor-kitchen' and dinning space opens freely to the lounge but the rest of the house still maintains a very private nighttime area (with a private corridor).

Figure 30 : Tour Nuage (1975), Emile Aillaude (1902-1988)

A variation is offered in DKV's building in Kop St. Janshaven Street (1986-1988) that places the dining area opposite to the lounge, with the corridor-kitchen in the middle, which results in a more private area.

This kind of solutions would become very useful when the architect searches for more versatility in the way dwellers appropriate their space, as we can see in the following examples.

Figure 31: Kop St. Janshaven (1986-1988), DKV

The Admiralstrasse Street building (1986), from Nylund, Puttfarken and Stürzebecher goes further, proposing a 22m² cooking/dining area. Its location, as an entrance space, indicates a public use where visitors are welcomed. The living room becomes a more secluded space, closed by a door and holding the stairs to the upper floor, where the rooms are.

Figure 32: Admiralstrasse, 16 (1986), Nylund, Puttfarken e Stürzebecher

The K25 building (1988-1992), from Zaaijer, Christiaanse and van De Born defines a small hallway but with immediate access to the 48m² dining room/kitchen where only the counter offers some sort of a limit between eating and cooking. Opposed to the kitchen there is still a living room with 20m² that can be closed, making this the truly private space within the public domestic areas. Contrarily to the Italians that during the 1950's Neo-realism used the kitchen as a family space, the 'Dutch' seem to prefer a leisure-only area to connect with their household members. Notice that it's possible to use the living room as an additional bedroom since it can be closed, but also because the dining area has enough space to be used as a lounge.

Figure 33: K25 (1988-1992), Zaaijer, Christiaanse e van De Born

The more radical solution seems to be to unite living room, dining room and kitchen in a single space, as in Galgebakken (1969-1974), in Denmark, by Stogard, Orum-Nielsen and Marcussen. All the domestic public life becomes public to outside visitors, even if there is a hall that protects the lounge from the front door that filters some prying-eyes. The nearby bathroom and office/bedroom makes possible to have visitors without them entering the household's private space, proving that even here there must be some sort of limit between 'outside public' and 'domestic public'.

Figure 34: Galgebakken (1969-1974), Zaaijer, Christiaanse e van De Born

10. Beyond the Family: fraternity and privacy

The perception in architecture of the existence of households beyond the family is a relatively recent phenomenon. The above mentioned causes lead to consider new spatial needs, because there are many reasons that lead to the coexistence under the same roof of families, generations, friends and strangers. The notion that you can't predict the precise type of dwellers destroys the last of Modernism's dogmas: the need for versatility, in order to be able to adapt to any kind of household, determines that spaces and rooms with a precise uses become obsolete.

College students and young adults are a good example of a new kind of household that demands a lot from a house. Friends and strangers share a series of services and spaces but also need privacy: a bedroom that is also a living and a reception room for visitors. The location and proportion of the rooms in a house are revised in order to create a space that is homogenous and innocuous in the sense that dwellers can use rooms as they please. A smaller lounge and bigger kitchen and rooms fit the above purposes but also the ones of a family that only spends their time at home during meals, being the rooms a leisure area (specially for children with their electronic paraphernalia).

This is why fraternity and privacy are opposites that come close together when blood-ties are no longer important in a house. The types and models from pre-Modern architecture become an example, with their undifferentiated spaces and multiple accesses for each room, and influence contemporary housing cells.

10.1 Bahnhofstrasse (1992)

The house as a dynamic organism is the premise of Florian Riegler e Roger Riewe (1954 - ...; 1959 - ...), who manage to use the same cell as two-bedroom or a four-bedroom apartment, just changing the location of the kitchen (with the necessary plumbing in both spaces). The countless doors among rooms allow that, whatever the chosen use, access can still me made without disturbing others privacy. And, according to evolving needs, altering the apartment becomes viable.

Figure 35: Bahnhofstrasse, (1992), Florian Riegler (1954 - ...) e Roger Riewe (1959 - ...)

10.2 Campo di Marte (1985)

Álvaro Siza (1933-...) also manages to vary the number of rooms within the same apartment, with physical changes kept to a minimum, in this case the addition of a wall. The lounge (or the bigger of the bedrooms) is divided into two spaces, creating two bedrooms with 8m^2 each. However, since this is a Mediterranean project, the idealization of the spaces is more conservative, where the kitchen maintains always its enclosed character. As in the above previous example dwellers still maintain their autonomy, but still function as a group. That wouldn't be the case in the next example.

Figure 36: Campo di Marte, Venezia (1985), Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...)

10.3 Kitagata (1994-1998)

The more unconventional proposal must be the one from Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...) that uses the bedroom as the module of the cell, not only in their measurements but also in their ideology. They have even their own outside entrance, making each dweller feel like they live in their own house inside a bigger one. The kitchen and the 'tatami' room are still the same for each one, but even so the household is composed like the sum of individual entities, like a group of persons living alone. The cell can still house a traditional family, but its range comprises all the household types.

Figure 36: Kitagata (1994 – 1998), Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...)

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